

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D9.3

Principles for impact assessment of
PILOTING against SoEL
requirements

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AESA	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea (“Spanish Agency for Aerial Safety”)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ATEX	Atmosphères Explosives
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line Of Sight
CAA	Civil Aviation Authority
CMR	Convention relative au contrat de transport international de marchandises par route (“Convention on the contract for the international carriage of goods by road”)
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DMS	Data Management System
DPO	Data Project Officer
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F2F	Face to face
FCA	Financial Conduct Authority
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HSE	Health & Safety Environment
I&M	Inspection and maintenance
IA	Impact Assessment
IECEEx	International Electrotechnical Commission System for Certification to Standards Relating to Equipment for Use in Explosive Atmospheres
IR	Infrared Camera
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IVP	Intelligent and Visualization Portal
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MTOW	Maximum Take-Off Weight
SoEL	Social, Ethical and Legal
SORA	Specific Operations Risk Assessment
SoTA	Safe and secure over-the-air
STS	Standard Scenarios
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle

UK	United Kingdom
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
US	United States
UTM	Unmanned aircraft system Traffic Management
VLOS	Visual Line of Sight
WP	Work Package

Table 1. Acronyms list

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable constitutes an update of the deliverable D9.1 and concerns the PILOTING project's social, ethical, and legal (SoEL) aspects.

The deliverable D9.1 identified, at the time of writing (June of 2020), the SoEL principles which applied to the PILOTING project, to set the requirements that constituted a benchmark against which project activities and outcomes were assessed, the "PILOTING Impact Assessment Framework".

The deliverable D9.3 aims to update the SoEL principles with any updates to legislation that have occurred in the last two years. Furthermore, currently, the third year of the project is underway, and the first development phase has been completed. The PILOTING consortium is now working on the integration and validation part of the PILOTING solution. In this stage of the project, the PILOTING consortium has a best knowledge of the final PILOTING solution and is able to analyse better the SoEL requirements that can be applied to the project.

Then, the "PILOTING Impact Assessment Framework" (guidelines for the impact assessment, which apply to each "PILOTING Impact scenario") defined in the D9.1 has been updated taking into account the new requirements identified.

Finally, this deliverable maintains the impact assessment methodology, which will occur in three phases: the initial phase consisting in setting the framework (the deliverables D9.1 and D9.3); performing the impact assessment during each iteration of the PILOTING project: each one corresponding to Deliverable 9.2 and 9.4 respectively; and the continuous monitoring of the impacts upon SoEL requirements.

1.2 Scope of the document

This deliverable provides operational guidelines of the ethical principles and main areas of applicable law and regulation in the context of the technologies that the PILOTING project intends to develop (autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence) and also with respect to data protection and privacy. This is done in order to provide PILOTING partners with a set of key notions that will serve as a reference to later assess the impact of the work of the project with respect to the relevant ethical and legal issues identified.

1.3 Structure of the document

This deliverable has the following sections:

- Section 1 presents the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.

- Section 2 checks any potential change in the PILOTING Impact Scenarios, in order to update the SoEL requirements considering the different types of pilots and geographical/legal implications.
- Section 3 updates the applicable SoEL principles for data protection and privacy impact, the European and national regulations for the operation of unmanned vehicles, and offers a generic view of the applicable regulations for the development of novel technologies such as artificial intelligence.
- Section 4 sets guidelines for the impact assessment for the *PILOTING Impact Scenario*.
- Section 5 provides details on the Impact Assessment (IA) methodology to be followed in the PILOTING project in order to determine the activities which require an IA and how will be done the evaluation, treatment, monitoring and review of impacts.
- Section 6 summarizes this document by including the main conclusions gathered.

2. Identification of the PILOTING Impact Scenarios

In the first review report, it was required to provide several methods and first guidelines for the impact assessment as well as show the differences among different types of pilots and geographical/legal implications. For this purpose, the PILOTING consortium worked on a new version of the deliverable, which defined the *PILOTING Impact Scenarios* (in Table 2, a reminder of the *PILOTING Impact Scenarios* has been included).

As mentioned in the deliverable D9.1, *PILOTING Impact Scenarios* involves the classification of the PILOTING Uses Cases differentiating by scenario and type of robotic solution developed. In this regard, have been employed to set the guidelines for the impact assessment, considering all the relevant principles of data protection (societal), legal and ethics that apply to the project outcomes and activities concerning their impact. There is not any modification in the *PILOTING Impact Scenarios* section since last version of D9.1.

PILOTING Scenario	PILOTING Use Case	Robot	Type of robotic solution	PILOTING Impact Scenario	Nº
Refineries	Refinery large structures inspection	AEROX	Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Refineries - UAV	1
	Refinery pipes inspection	HYBRID	Hybrid (UAV and Crawler)		
	Refinery vessels inspection	BIKE	Crawler		
	Refinery ground monitoring	RISING	Ground vehicle (UGV)	Refineries - UGV	3
Bridges/Viaducts	Viaduct visual inspection	AERO-CAM	Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Bridges/viaduct - UAV	4
	Viaduct bearings inspection	VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)		

	Viaduct – Sensor installation	VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)		
	Viaduct – Surveying targets installation for geometrical precise measurements	VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)		
Tunnel	Tunnel local inspection	TT-DRONE	Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Tunnel – UAV	5
	Tunnel general inspection	CART	Ground vehicle (UGV)	Tunnel – UGV	6

Table 2. PILOTING Impact Scenarios.

The social, ethical and legal aspects are the same as described in deliverable D9.1 since (PILOTING technological developments have been carried out according to plan). However, the PILOTING consortium has made an exhaustive review of the information that could affect any of the defined SoEL requirements:

- **The Social aspects:** As was described in the D9.1, in PILOTING, the applicable privacy and data protection framework acknowledge the participation of external participants in project activities (like workshops, demo sessions or surveys) and the use of onboard sensors that can capture data from the environment. PILOTING partners made an exhaustive analysis of which on-board sensors in the PILOTING robotic solutions could generate a SoEL issue regarding the possibility of them taking any sensitive external data. There has been no update with respect to D9.1, as it is listed below:
 - **Operational Camera.** A visual camera employs to carry out the inspection, detecting infrastructure defects.
 - **Situational awareness camera.** A visual camera is employed to help the operator/inspector to localise the robot during the inspection process.
 - **Infrared camera (IR).** An IR camera uses to detect and measure the infrared energy of objects. IR cameras detect these invisible infrared wavelengths, enabling the camera to see in the dark.
 - **LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging).** A remote sensing method that uses light in the form of a pulsed laser to measure ranges (variable distances) and generates a point cloud that makes it possible to distinguish objects.

Table 3 shows which of these sensors is on-board each PILOTING robot. From the last version of this table (included in the D9.1), just the HYBRID robot has incorporated an additional sensor: a situational awareness camera.

PILOTING Robotic Vehicles	Operational Camera	Situational awareness camera	Infrared Camera	Lidar
AEROX	X	X		

AERO-CAM	X	X		X
VIAD-DRONE	X	X		
CART	X			X
TT-DRONE	X			
RISING	X		X	X
BIKE	X			X
HYBRID	X	X		X

Table 3. On-board sensor in each PILOTING robotic solution.

- **Ethical aspects:** Concerning the ethical aspect, the regulatory framework which apply is still the one related to novel technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI). Any updates that may have been made in relation to this regulation have been included in this deliverable.
- **Legal aspects:** Concerning the legal aspect, the European legal and regulatory framework which apply is related to the use of Unmanned vehicles (UAV and UGV). A more exhaustive analysis of this regulatory and legal framework has been included in this deliverable.

3. Identification of the applicable SoEL requirements

This section summarizes all the applicable SoEL principles regarding legal, data protection and privacy, and ethics within the PILOTING project, updating, to which it is applicable, the information provided in the deliverable D9.1.

The main update of the current deliverable is includes a detailed description of the applicable ATEX regulation related to the performance of equipment for potentially explosive atmospheres.

3.1 Identification of the applicable SoEL principles for the Data Protection and Privacy impact assessment

As mentioned in deliverable D9.1, the main applicable regulation for Data Protection in all PILOTING countries is still the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1]. It is important to highlight that no changes have been carried out in this regulation since the last Periodic Report.

The description of the applicable ethics regulations for data protection and privacy and the procedures followed in PILOTING can be found in the deliverables D9.1 y WP1 “Ethics requirements” deliverables.

In this deliverable, a summary of the main applicable principles that apply to the PILOTING project is reminded.

3.1.1 GDPR definition [1]

The full name of this legislation is Regulation 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing directive 95/46/EC.

The GDPR applies to the processing of all personal data of individuals residing in EU member states. It does not apply to the processing of personal data "by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties" which specifically includes "the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security and the free movement of such data". Nor does it apply to processing of a purely personal or household activity with no connection to a professional or commercial activity. Finally, it does not apply to processing related to activities outside Union law, including activities concerning national security.

On the other hand, GDPR defines specific personal data as data that are mostly related to sensitive and peculiar aspect of the personality of physical subjects, and notably: genetic data, biometric data: and data concerning health.

Furthermore, processing of personal data being able to reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation are, in general, prohibited and may be processed exclusively in some specific cases. These categories of personal data are subject to additional protections, as they are considered as the hardcore of the protection that must be ensured to citizens by privacy regulations.

Anonymous information is not covered by the EU Regulation. Whereas n. 26 states that "The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. This regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes".

The main regulatory actors concerned with privacy and data protection.

Although Regulation 2016/679 is a European legislative initiative, the main regulatory bodies it foresees for the enforcement of data protection law are established at the national level. These take the form of National Data Protection Authorities (sometimes known as 'National Data Protection Commissioners')

Data roles

The PILOTING Data Roles were defined in D1.2- POPD-Requirement N°2:

- Controller: "natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State

law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law"

- Processor: "a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller".
- Data Protection Officer: appointed by the PILOTING consortium "according to the professional qualities, in particular of the specialized knowledge of the legislation and practices regarding data protection" (art. 37, par. 5 GDPR). This appointment is stated in deliverable D1.2- POPD-Requirement N°2.

Legal Basis for the processing of personal data

Article 6 of the GDPR demands that the processing of personal data must have a legal basis to be lawfully processed. In order to comply with such requirements personal data may be processed for one of the following reasons:

- the data subject has unambiguously given his consent; or
- processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract; or
- processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject; or
- processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject; or
- processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller or in a third party to whom the data are disclosed; or
- processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by the third party or parties to whom the data are disclosed, except where such interests are overridden by the interests for fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection. [2]

3.2 European and national legal framework on Unmanned Vehicles

PILOTING project experiments must comply with European Drone Regulation.

On 11 June 2019 common European rules on drones, Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 & Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 [3], were published by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) to ensure drone operations across Europe are safe and secure. The rules will amongst others, help to protect the safety and the privacy of EU citizens while enabling the free circulation of drones and a level playing field within the European Union.

The new rules include technical as well as operational requirements for drones. On the one hand, they define the capabilities a drone must have to be flown safely. For instance, new drones will have to be individually identifiable, allowing the authorities to trace a particular drone if necessary.

On the other hand, the rules cover each operation type, from those not requiring prior authorisation, to those involving certified aircraft and operators, as well as minimum remote pilot training requirements.

While the EU regulation was published in June 2019, it was not until 30 December 2020 when it came into force. Therefore, it has been applicable when experiments or pilot tests are carried out in PILOTING.

In the deliverable D9.1, the categories of operation defined by the new European regulation were described, and the categories that apply to the different PILOTING Impact Scenarios (see deliverable D9.1, Section 4.3, Table 5). In summary, in the PILOTING project, the developed aerial platforms will be within the categories “open” or “specific”.

In this new version of the deliverable, PILOTING consortium has completed a more detailed analysis, defining the operational requirements within each category applicable in PILOTING.

Open category

For the “open” category, EASA has defined the following subcategories:

- A1: where it is possible to fly over people but not over assemblies of people
- A2: fly close to people
- A3: fly far from people

The following requirements apply to each of the three subcategories:

UAS		Operation		Drone operator/pilot		
Max weight	Subcategory	Operational restrictions		Drone operator registration	Remote pilot competence	Remote pilot minimum age
< 250 g	A1 (can also fly in subcategory A3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No flight expected over uninvolved people (if it happens, overflight should be minimised) — No flight over assemblies of people 		No, unless camera / sensor on board and the drone is not a toy	— No training required	No minimum age
< 500 g				Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Proof of completion for online training' for A1/A3 'open' subcategory 	16*
< 2 kg	A2 (can also fly in subcategory A3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No flying over uninvolved people — Keep a horizontal distance of 50 m from uninvolved people 		Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Remote pilot certificate of competency' for A2 'open' subcategory 	16*
< 25 kg	A3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Do not fly near or over people — Fly at least 150 m away from residential, commercial or industrial areas 		Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Proof of completion for online training' for A1/A3 'open' subcategory 	16*

Figure 1: Subcategories within the Open category (source EASA [4]).

Specific category

With respect to the Specific category, two main options are considered in the European Drone Regulation:

- Standard Scenario. This option has the advantage that only a responsible declaration is required to operate, and it is not needed to get through a complete authorisation process with the National Aviation Authority (much slower). Right now, there are two approved standard scenarios:
 - STS 1: VLOS operation in an urban environment but with ground-controlled area.
 - STS 2: BVLOS operation (until 2Km with observers) in a sparsely populated environment.

From January 2024, these two scenarios can only be operated with C5 and C6 labelled drones. Until that moment, national standard scenarios, if exist, apply with some specific limitations. For example, in Spain, the national standard scenario STS-01-ES only allows to fly drones up to 10Kg, and not 25Kg, as will happen with C5 labelled drones.

- Operational authorisation. This option requires to go through a complete authorisation process with the national aviation authority. Moreover, it requires to implement a full UAS operator structure and procedures within the organisation that will act as drone operator, which also has an important impact in terms of efforts and resources. On the positive side, this option may not require to use a labelled drone, which offers more flexibility and decreases the needed investment on the aerial platform to start offering inspection services.

3.3 Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV)

This section briefly summarises the potential applicable regulation to autonomous road vehicles.

As mentioned in the D9.1, robots for infrastructure inspection and maintenance covered within the PILOTING project will operate in private and off-road settings, so many of the regulations concerning autonomous vehicles may not apply. In most jurisdictions, autonomous ground vehicles that are meant to operate without humans on board must be tested on private property for the time being, which will be comply in all the PILOTING validation experiments.

In previous deliverable (D9.1), an overview was given of the evolution of road vehicles legislation since the Vienna Convention on Road Traffic [5], passing by the Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road (CMR) [6], until the UNECE World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations [7]. Also discussed was the EU motivation and efforts to harmonise regulations in order to reach a shared buy-in that would result in consistent implementations and interpretations, and to overcome the lag behind other major markets such as the US and China. For further information, please review this deliverable.

This deliverable updates the information provided, making a deeply analysis of the UGV regulation. In addition, it is important to highlight that, in the absence of legislation regulating UGV developments carried out in PILOTING in the applicable operating environment, PILOTING consortium envisages the possibility of using the “regulatory sandbox” tool, which serves to legislate and promote new concepts and technologies and it has been presented in the section 3.5.

On the UGV regulation and most recent standards, the PILOTING consortium rely mostly on **the ISO 3691-4:2020**, which can be seen as a Standard for automated guided vehicles.

The norm ISO 3691-4:2020 is titled Industrial Trucks – Safety requirements and verification Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems. Such document specifies safety requirements and the means for their verification for driverless industrial trucks (hereafter referred to as trucks) and their systems. According to the norm, examples of driverless industrial trucks (trucks of ISO 5053-1) can also be known as: "automated guided vehicle", "autonomous mobile robot", "bots", "automated guided cart", "tunnel tugger", "under cart", etc.

In summary, the norm is applicable to “trucks” designed to operate automatically and **not applicable** to trucks guided by mechanical means or to remotely controlled trucks, which are not consider to be driverless trucks.

We should also consider a number of auxiliary norms that are directly embedded in the previous one, such as:

- ISO 12100:2010 Risk assesment and risk reduction
- ISO 13849-1:2015 Safety-related parts of control systems
- ISO 13857:2008 Safety distances to prevent Hazard zones being reached by upper and lower limbs
- ISO 4413:2010 Hydraulic fluid power
- ISO 4414:2010 Pneumatic fluid power
- ISO 13856-2/-3:2013 Pressure-sensitive protective
- ISO 22915-7: 2016 Verification of stability (Part 7: Bidirectional and multidirectional trucks)
- ISO 13850:2015 Emergency stop function
- ISO 15870:2000 Powered industrial trucks
- ISO 13856-2/-3:2013 Pressure-sensitive protective
- ISO 61496-2:2013 Electro-sensitive protective equipment (Part 2: Particular requirements for equipment using active opto-electronic protective devices (AOPDs))
- ISO 61496-2:2013 Electro-sensitive protective equipment (Part 3: Particular requirements for Active opto-electronic protective devices responsive to diffuse reflection (AOPDDR))
- ISO 61204-1:2006 Electrical equipment of machines
- EN 1175-1:1998 +A1:2010 Electrical equipment (Part 1: General requirements for battery powered trucks)
- EN 12895:2015 Electromagnetic compatibility

Apart from that, the norm describes different procedures and features to comply with, mainly related with stability, speed control, person detection, braking systems etc. As examples, most important issues to consider are:

- Related with braking system, the truck shall be equipped with a braking system that is designed to do the following:
 - Operate on the interruption of the power supply
 - Activate automatically at the loss of control of the speed or steering
 - Stop the truck within the operating range of the personnel detection means in the worst conditions
 - Maintain the truck and its maximum specific load stationary on the maximum operational gradient
- Related with detection of person in the intended path in automatic mode
 - Trucks shall be fitted with pressure-sensitive device according

- Personnel detection means shall operate at least over the maximum width of the truck and its load in the direction of travel.
- Personnel detection means shall be so designed that trucks shall stop before contact between the rigid parts of the truck or load and a stationary person and comply with annexed values or in case of contact they shall be designed such that forces shall not exceed the values defined. In turning direction and in pivoting direction, for the truck side protection measures, compliance with different values is sufficient.
- The truck may restart automatically following appropriated warnings (e.g. optical and/or acoustic). If PSPE a delay of 2 seconds is required before restart. Automatic restart shall only be possible according to the “automatic restart permitted”
- In the direction of the actuation of the protective device cannot be possible:
 - Maximum speed 0.3 m/s
 - Additional stop function within 600 mm from the hazardous point.

Additional information and standards can be found in the document regarding stability of the load, signalling, information management and other operating conditions.

To sum up, the **ISO 3691-4:2020** extensively compiles all the aspects and security requirements that matters towards a safe and reliable use of ground mobile robots. This can be seen indeed as a Standard for automated guided vehicles that could be used to guide the possible legal requirements that could be applied in the future to the UGVs developed within PILOTING project.

3.4 Artificial Intelligence

As was introduced in the D9.1, Artificial intelligence (AI) has become an area of strategic importance and a key driver of economic development. It can bring solutions to many societal challenges, but it is essential to join forces in the EU to stay at the forefront of this technological revolution, to ensure competitiveness and to shape the conditions for its development and use (ensuring respect of European values) [8].

In the last four years, the EU has been very active in fostering the development of artificial intelligence and until July 2021, the main principles to be followed (to the EU) had been summarised in the "**Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**" [9].

In this deliverable, the main advances made in AI regulation since June 2020 are discussed.

On 9th October 2020 the Second European AI Alliance Assembly took place. This event focused on the latest achievements and future projections of the EU policies on Artificial Intelligence. In this event, the results from the AI White Paper [10] consultation were shown to the public. This session also included plenaries and parallel workshops and breakout sessions. The main conclusion retrieved from this event, according to some experts, is that the European Commission is moving forward on the right path towards the future of AI Regulation and remarking that the European values need to be preserved in the framework of the regulation.

The European Commission presented a proposal for AI regulation named “Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL LAYING DOWN HARMONISED RULES ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT) AND AMENDING CERTAIN UNION LEGISLATIVE ACTS (the AI ACT)” in July 2021 [11]. This proposal is intended to be a step forward in global AI regulation from the European Union. With this regulation, the EU became the first governmental institution in the world to issue a comprehensive response in the form of draft regulations aimed specifically at the development and use of AI. The regulation would apply to every AI system used in the EU, showing implications for organizations all over the world.

The European Union’s draft AI regulations divides the risk associated to AI in three main categories depending on their different uses of AI systems [12]:

1. Unacceptable-risk AI systems.

Unacceptable risk of AI systems is the highest level of risk. It contains three prohibited uses of AI. These uses will be subliminal, manipulative, or exploitative systems that cause harm, remote biometric identification systems used in public spaces for law enforcement, and all forms of social scoring.

2. High-risk AI systems.

High-risk AI systems consist in various systems that could produce worrying effects in the society. The high-risk AI systems will be review and updated by the European Union. These risks include, social creditworthiness evaluation systems, recruiting or employee-management systems, biometric identification in nonpublic spaces or systems used in administration of justice.

3. Limited and minimal-risk AI systems.

Finally, in the limited or minimal risk level can be found chatbots, spam filters, customer and market segmentation systems and almost every other AI system.

The draft regulation proposes different requirements for the AI systems developed depending on their level of risk. The first case, Unacceptable-risk AI Systems will not be allowed in the European Union. Moreover, the largest set of requirements will be applied to the High-risk systems. Among these requirements in organizations that use or provide these High-risks AI systems, some of them can be remarked:

- Implementation of a risk-management system.
- Data governance and management.
- Technical documentation.
- Record keeping and logging.
- Transparency and provision of information to users.

The oversight obligations imposed by the draft regulation on those providing or using high-risk systems include:

- Conformity assessments.
- Ensuring that these systems are explainable, monitorable and operate consistently throughout their lifetime.
- Establishing an organization-wide cyber risk management practice.

Finally, limited and minimal-risk AI systems will have fewer requirements due to its low implications in society and personal data. Most of the requirements from this category will be related to transparency obligations. The set of requirements that aim to create awareness will apply to all risk categories.

It is important to point out that PILOTING AI technological developments will be under limited and minimal-risk AI systems since they do not handle personal data (see Section 4.2). Then, this will facilitate the future exploitation of these technologies.

3.5 Regulatory sandbox

Recently a new policy instrument has started to be explored by the different European governments in order to validate new technologies and solutions without having to wait to have a complete regulation approved to start offering services and products using novel technologies. This is the so-called 'sandbox'. Its name comes from the well-known playground enclosure full of sand where children can experiment in a controlled environment. The idea for the regulatory sandbox is the same: to provide a relatively delimited, safe and controlled space in which projects, solutions or services can be tested without being subject to the rules that in some way would be hindering or preventing these tests from being carried out [13].

Although no commonly agreed definition exists, regulatory sandboxes can be broadly described as schemes that enable firms to test innovations in a controlled real-world environment, under a specific plan developed and monitored by a competent authority. Regulatory sandboxes are a relatively new policy instrument. They are part of efforts by regulators across the globe to tackle regulatory challenges generated by technological transformation, and the emergence of new products, services and business models [14].

This idea has been gradually adopted by regulatory authorities, with the financial sector being the first one to use it. An example of this is the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), which is the conduct regulator for around 51,000 financial services firms and financial markets in the UK. Its Regulatory Sandbox, launched in 2016, allows firms to test innovative propositions in the market with real consumers. The sandbox is open to authorised firms, unauthorised firms that require authorisation, and technology businesses. It seeks to provide firms with: the ability to test products and services in a controlled environment; reduced time-to-market at potentially lower cost; support in identifying appropriate consumer protection safeguards to build into new products and services; and better access to finance. It is open for applications at any point throughout the year since August 2021 [15].

This legal tool has more recently arrived in the aerospace field. In April 2019, the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA), UK's aviation regulator, launched the Innovation Hub to help innovators bring their

new aviation and travel products and services to market with new rulesets and standards that underpin regulatory approvals taking too long to emerge [16]. One of the Innovation Hub's instruments for this purpose is its Regulatory Sandbox. It works through 'Challenges' proposed by the CAA itself or by other entities. These Challenges, concerning topics such as Future Air Mobility, Detect and Avoid or UTM, provide a pathway to seek approval for the trial of innovative solutions and shape the requirements for future regulations. The Sandbox helps to maximise regulatory readiness by ensuring development activities address the key risks and unknowns that innovation brings in terms of safety, security and consumer protection [17].

At a higher governmental level, it has been more complex to integrate this instrument in a completely defined and unified way.

As for the European Union, the Council published in November 2020 a set of conclusions on regulatory sandboxes and experimentation clauses as tools for an innovation-friendly, future-proof and resilient regulatory framework that masters disruptive challenges in the digital age. The Council called on the European Commission (EC) to organise, in cooperation with Member States, an exchange of information and good practices regarding regulatory sandboxes between Member States and itself in order to: establish an overview of the state of play regarding the use of regulatory sandboxes in the EU; identify experiences regarding the legal basis, implementation and evaluation of regulatory sandboxes; analyse how learning from regulatory sandboxes at national level can contribute to evidence-based policy making at EU-level [18].

The Commission answered to this request through the Working Party on 'Better Regulation', and presented an analysis on regulatory sandboxes at the 'Better regulation' toolbox report (November 2021). This document provides an overview of what a sandbox is, why it is relevant for policymaking, recent examples of regulatory sandboxes in the EU and elements to consider before setting them up. It is also remarked that existing regulatory sandboxes are limited to specific policy areas (e.g. financial services, energy, digital technologies) and usually implemented locally, as this is where the regulator can more easily control the parameters of the sandbox experiment. One of the main difficulties of a regulatory sandbox is to scale-up the results observed in the testing environment to the wider market. At EU level, an additional challenge is worth mentioning: the impact on the Single Market and the risk of fragmentation if sandboxes for the same innovation are implemented in an uncoordinated manner in different Member States. This risk is already known to regulators and various approaches are being considered to mitigate it [14].

3.5.1 Examples of Sandboxes aligned with PILOTING project technologies

Some recent examples of the implementation of sandboxes in the EU, in addition to those mentioned from the United Kingdom, are:

Regarding UAV technologies:

- Transport of medical samples by drone: The regulatory sandbox Medifly Hamburg allows for the transportation of sample tissue between hospitals located in the same urban area. The

sandbox is backed by the Hamburg Authority for Economy, Transport and Innovation, and involves Hamburg's aviation authority and the relevant air traffic control office [14].

Regarding IA technologies:

As described in the previous section, there is still important work to be done in the field of artificial intelligence at the regulatory level. For this reason, several examples of sandboxes are appearing in European countries to avoid the Technology vs. Policy law gap.

- Artificial Intelligence Act (AI ACT) [11]: Article 53 of the Commission's proposal (COM/2021/206 final) provides the general framework for the formal establishment and operation of artificial intelligence (AI) regulatory sandboxes by one or more Member States competent authorities or the European Data Protection Supervisor [14].

For example, in Spain (one of the places where the PILOTING demonstrations will be performed) a regulatory Sandbox was presented by the Spanish government and the European Commission at an event held in Brussels in the last week of June 2022. This sandbox aims to bring competent authorities closer to companies that develop AI with the goal of defining best practices to guide the implementation of future European Commission's AI Regulation. The legislation is expected to be implemented within two years.

The regulatory sandbox will connect the main Innovators and regulators providing a controlled environment for them to increase cooperation. This cooperation will improve the development, testing and validation of new AI systems within the requirements of the new AI Regulation.

Tests will begin in October 2022 to collect experience and the results will be presented in the second half of 2023 during the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU. The presentation will consist of best practices and implementation guidelines to be made available to all Member States and the European Commission, to be used in the preparation of the implementation of the future AI Regulation.

Other European countries are in the process of developing their own AI Sandbox. Two countries stand out in this regard in the European Zone: Switzerland and Norway.

Swiss Innovation Sandbox initiative aims to strike a balance between regulation and innovation towards AI projects. This initiative is being implemented by organizations, companies and institutions in a framework controlled by the cantonal administration. The organizations that want to participate in this initiative had to submit their AI projects between March and June 2022. In total, 21 AI projects were received to be evaluated.

From July 2022, AI projects were selected and will be implemented in cooperation with partners such as authorities, cities or municipalities in the Zurich metropolitan area. The projects affected by this regulation are: Regulatory Support and Data Provision AI projects. The project submitted will be evaluated based on uniform criteria [19].

The most remarkable issue about this AI initiative is that the knowledge extracted from the projects will be made publicly available and the results will be used to build up the administration AI skills in order to add value to the AI sector organizations by clarifying the regulatory basis.

Following the British AI Sandbox model, the Norwegian Data Protection Authority's Regulatory Sandbox [20] will increase the innovation of responsible Artificial Intelligence initiatives. The main objective of this regulation is to promote the development and implementation of ethical and responsible AI from privacy perspective. In order to achieve this goal, the regulatory Sandbox aims to produce benefits for organizations, individuals and society. The Norwegian regulator has identified three main characteristics to be fulfilled by the future AI projects:

- Lawful: Respecting all applicable laws and regulations.
- Ethical: Respecting ethical principles and values.
- Robust: Implementing a technical perspective but, also, taking into account the social environment.

It is important to mention that these three main principles are based on the "Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI" published by the European Commission AI High Level Expert Group.

3.5.2 Other types of Sandboxes implemented in PILOTING partner's countries:

- Pilot Regime for Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) market infrastructures: The proposed Regulation on DLT market infrastructures aims to enable market participants to operate a DLT market infrastructure (either a DLT multilateral trading facility or a DLT securities settlement system) under certain conditions [14].
- Facilitating innovative projects for collective self-consumption of electricity: A derogation to articles L. 315-2 and L 315-3 of the Energy Code aims to facilitate the development of innovative projects in the area of collective self-consumption of electricity. The sandbox runs for five years and is operated under France Experimentation, an initiative by the French Ministry of Economy and Finance [14].
- Pan-European blockchain regulatory sandbox: The EU Member States, Norway and Liechtenstein signed a Declaration creating the European Blockchain Partnership to establish a European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI) and support the delivery of cross-border digital public services, with the highest standards of security and privacy [14].

Member States of the EU are also working on their own legislation to allow regulatory sandboxes to become a reality. German's Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy published in July 2019 Making space for innovation: The handbook for regulatory sandboxes. It shows the variety of ways in which regulatory sandboxes are used and provides recommendations and practical examples. It is addressed to companies, research establishments and administrations planning and implementing a specific regulatory sandbox, and also to legislative bodies wishing to put the legal basis in place for regulatory sandboxes [21]. Moreover, in Spain, the Preliminary Draft of the Sustainable Mobility Law was published in February 2022, whose Title V regulates a sandbox or controlled space for regulatory testing in the field of transport and mobility, aimed at regulatory innovation, to the extent that its purpose is for the administration to be aware of the innovative activity proposed by the

promoter, assess its adaptation to the current regulatory framework and adopt, if necessary, the regulatory amendments that may be necessary [22].

In short: the authorities are putting all their efforts into renewing legislation to adapt it to the new reality and thus facilitate the innovative work of companies. This legislative revolution, which has already begun, will mean a paradigm shift in terms of technological validation. Within the framework of the PILOTING project, this new legal tool may be beneficial in case of exploitation and industrialization of new technologies that do not have yet a regulation in place to be operated.

3.6 ATEX certification

For all the considered inspection operations in the Oil&Gas sector, such as PILOTING use cases related to the Refinery scenario, it is tremendously important to consider the operation of the robotic systems in explosive atmosphere environments.

The regulatory framework to this matter is the ATEX Directive 2014/34/EU, which covers equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres. The directive defines the essential health and safety requirements and conformity assessment procedures, to be applied before products are placed on the EU market. It is aligned with the new legislative framework policy, and it is applicable from 20 April 2016, replacing the previous Directive 94/9/EC. [23]

This Directive shall apply to the following ‘products’: [24]

- (a) equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres;
- (b) safety devices, controlling devices and regulating devices intended for use outside potentially explosive atmospheres but required for or contributing to the safe functioning of equipment and protective systems with respect to the risks of explosion;
- (c) components intended to be incorporated into equipment and protective systems referred to in point (a).

This Directive, as its precedent, establishes the criteria determining the classification of equipment-groups into categories, depending on the area of performance: [24]

1. Equipment-group I

- a. Category M 1: intended for use in underground parts of mines as well as those parts of surface installations of such mines endangered by firedamp and/or combustible dust.
- b. Category M 2: intended for use in underground parts of mines as well as those parts of surface installations of such mines likely to be endangered by firedamp and/or combustible dust.

2. Equipment-group II

- a. Category 1: intended for use in areas in which explosive atmospheres caused by mixtures of air and gases, vapors or mists or by air/dust mixtures are present continuously, for long periods or frequently.

- b. Category 2: intended for use in areas in which explosive atmospheres caused by gases, vapors, mists or air/dust mixtures are likely to occur occasionally.
- c. Category 3: intended for use in areas in which explosive atmospheres caused by gases, vapors, mists, or air/dust mixtures are unlikely to occur or, if they do occur, are likely to do so only infrequently and for a short period only.

When a company performs a work on a refinery, there are two main approaches:

- Use ATEX-certified tools. ATEX certification is given to equipment that has gone through rigorous testing outlined by European Union directives and proved safe to use in specific environments with explosive atmospheres, according to the zone/s they are certified to be used in. Certification can be gained via Notified bodies or through self-certification. [26]
- Use hot-work permits implementing emergency operational procedures. Due to the difficulty of apply ATEX in some equipment, Oil&Gas industry has started to design emergency operational procedures to use non-ATEX equipment in hazardous areas

Despite the information exposed, it is important to mention that ATEX certification have been granted to UGVs for inspection in environments with explosive atmospheres.

On one hand, [Taurob company](#) achieved the ATEX certification for some of their developments. Taurob develops and offers fully autonomous ground robots for routine operations and inspection on industrial sites. This company has entered its business around innovation to help customers tackle their everyday challenges on safety and improving their efficiency. In this sense, they have established a plan with to different phases:

- Offshore Ground Robot Industrial Pilot (OGRIP) – (2018-2020). During this phase were developed its Taurob inspection robot as well as Taurob tracker (analyse robotics solution in the company website), ensuring that they meet ATEX certification standards. After many tests on-site, these robots obtained the ATEX Zone 1 certified. These robots have operated in and Shetland Gas Plant.
- Offshore Work Class Robot Project (OWCR). As part of this phase, it is expected to be able to perform autonomous manipulation operations. The OWRC will be certified with ATEX and IECEx licenses.

On another hand, [ANYmalX](#), company that develop automatic inspections in Oil&Gas and chemicals facilities, has robotics solution that a good mobility, performance, and functionality and is Ex-certified for Zone 1 usage according to the IECEx and ATEX standards.

These first cases to certify UGVs in Oil&Gas set a precedent to the future licenses for tests and operations in environments with explosives atmospheres. Then, we already know that it is possible that the technologies, developed at PILOTING and related with UGV, could be ATEX certified in the future. This helps us when defining potential value propositions and business cases.

However, in the case of UAS or aerial robots it is different since there is no ATEX certified drone in the market. We have studied in detail this possibility, including conversations with a Notified Body

(such as TÜV Nord), and we have concluded that the current ATEX norm does not allow the certification of an aerial system since just the potential energy of the aerial vehicle (required to fly) is enough to provoke an explosion in case of contacting with structures of the refinery. Then, the approach for the future exploitation in the case of UAS should focus on hot work permits or operating in non-ATEX areas (like for example tanks).

4. Guidelines for the impact assessment

Once the "PILOTING SoEL Impact Assessment Framework" against assessing the project outcomes and activities has been defined, this section provides specific guidelines to complete the impact assessment and ensure the development of the project in a socially, ethically and legally acceptable way.

4.1 Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects

As presented above, the main legislation applicable concerning privacy and data protection framework is the **GDPR**, which applies to all PILOTING countries.

In the framework of the project, no changes have been included during this period. Then, a summary of the guidelines for impact assessment is reminded.

In PILOTING there are two potential ways in which data can be collected from external participants:

Data collected from participants in project activities. The project involves the participation of humans in various activities like workshops, surveys or pilot demo sessions.

Data capture from the on-board sensors. In order to set the applicable principles for each impact scenario, the type of data captured by each of the on-board sensors that may pose a SoEL issue (see section 2) has been analysed:

- **Operational Camara.** This type of sensor can collect images. In PILOTING, it will be used for a dual purpose:
 - **Detailed inspection.** The objective is to inspect defects or infrastructure components and its type of lens has been configured for short scope. In this configuration, the camera can only see clearly what is close to the lens and blurs distant objects. Then, even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place, it would not be possible to capture any personal data. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that this camera will only record the images indicated by the operator/inspector, which will only be focused on the defects to be analysed.
 - **General inspection.** The objective is to inspect the infrastructure and its type of lens has been configured for wide scope. This camera will be used for obtaining a general overview of the structure and to detect possible defects, so it would be able to visualise what is around the infrastructure. However, only images of the infrastructure, previously indicated by the operator/inspector, will be recorded.

Then, even if there were a person in the vicinity of where the inspection is taking place, any personal data would be collected.

- **Situational awareness camera.** This type of sensor can collect images. However, the situational awareness camera will serve as a support to visually assist the operator/inspector in positioning the robotic vehicle with respect to the infrastructure to be inspected. The image will be focused on the drone components/infrastructure and will not record any type of data.
- **Infrared camera (IR).** IR cameras detect these invisible infrared wavelengths, enabling the camera to see images in the dark. Nevertheless, if a person is caught by the sensors, these images are not clear enough to identify any sensitive data. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed.
- **LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging):** the LIDAR sensor generates a point cloud that allows objects to be identified. However, if a person is detected, it will not be possible to distinguish any personal data (sex, race, etc), because the cloud point generated by this sensor does not have enough resolution. In addition, only data from the infrastructure will be analysed and processed.

In addition, it is important to highlight that during the pilot experiments, the scenarios will be restricted, and no external personnel are expected to enter the area during the missions. Then, it is not expected to collect personal data during the project's technical activities or even in future exploitation activities using PILOTING technologies. However, if personal data are collected, the GDPR must be applied.

Then and following the GDPR, when personal data will be collected from external participants:

- Informed consent procedures must be defined and implemented.
- The access to the data collected must be restricted only to authorised personnel.
- Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties.
- A Data Project Officer (DPO) must be appointed (which has been already done; see deliverable D1.2, Section 2.4.1).

4.2 Guidelines for the impact assessment in Ethical Aspects

As mentioned in Deliverable 9.1, regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to AI technologies. Currently, the European Commission is working in a proposal for an AI Regulation, which aims to ensure the protection of fundamental rights and user safety, as well as trust in the development and uptake of AI.

Concerning the ethical aspects, the main principles to be followed (defined so far) has been summarised in the "**Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**" [9] and in the **AI ACT** proposed by the EC. These are:

Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI

- Respect for human autonomy

- Prevention of harm
- Fairness
- Explicability

AI ACT

In July 2021, a proposal for the EU IA regulation was published. This regulation considers three main categories in which risks can be classified according to the new AI ACT proposed by the European Commission. In the following table, these three main risks are detailed and assessed with respect to PILOTING project.

Type of risk	EU requirements	AI risk in PILOTING project
Unacceptable risk	Unacceptable-risk AI Systems will not be allowed in the European Union. Must be avoided.	<p>None of the tasks carried out by the PILOTING solution involve an unacceptable AI risk since, the activities developed in the operation of PILOTING I&M platform is focused on the inspection of defect's infrastructures where people isn't involved.</p> <p>The use of the AI algorithms developed within the project will be not subliminal, manipulative, or exploitative and will not cause harm or remote biometric identification.</p>
High risk	<p>A large set of requirements will be applied to the High-risk systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of a risk-management system. • Data governance and management. • Technical documentation. • Record keeping and logging. • Transparency and provision of information to users. 	<p>Likewise, none of the tasks carried out by the PILOTING solution involve a high AI risk.</p> <p>The use of the AI algorithms developed within the project does not include social creditworthiness evaluation systems, recruiting or employee-management systems, biometric identification in non-public spaces or systems used in administration of justice.</p>
Limited and minimal risk	Transparency obligations	The category that best fits the purpose of the PILOTING Project belongs to "Limited and minimal risk AI Systems" and can be related to "Most other AI systems" since

		<p>there is no specific field of application defined for I&M or autonomous navigation use of Artificial Intelligence.</p> <p>PILOTING consortium is committed to monitor the algorithms developed within the framework of the project and their potential applications, ensuring that they comply with all the transparency obligations and remains in this category.</p>
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Table 4. AI risk categories stated in the AI ACT regulation.

Within PILOTING, an AI system for inspection analytics, which will be integrated in all the PILOTING robotic solutions, will be developed. This AI software performs inspection data analytics using advanced AI algorithms. These algorithms will be focused only on the detection of infrastructures defects. Then, this AI software will comply with all the ethical principles defined by the EC.

4.3 Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspects

As was included in Deliverable 9.1, regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the use of unmanned vehicles. However, this deliverable also deeply considers the operation on some of the PILOTING Uses Cases in Oil&Gas facilities, analysing the necessity of applying ATEX certification.

UAV

PILOTING project experiments must comply with **European Drone Regulation**. As defined, in PILOTING project, the platforms developed will be within the categories "open" or "specific" and must always comply with the specifications defined in this regulation. Analysing each PILOTING Scenario:

Refineries

The Specific category applies to the Refinery UAV inspection use cases, since the refinery is France is in a no-fly zone (due to the criticality of the infrastructure) and only operations under the Specific category are allowed.

Bridges/Viaducts

The UAS that operate in the Bridges/Viaducts scenario can operate on the Open or Specific category depending mainly if the operation is performed under VLOS or BVLOS rules. VLOS operations always require that the ground pilot has a direct visual line of sight of the UAS. However, depending on the procedure to operate the UAS for the bridge/viaduct inspection, this condition can or cannot be fulfilled. In fact, VLOS operations are possible but make the inspection procedure much slower. Then, we plan to start with VLOS operations and switch to BVLOS operations to evaluate the potential of using UAS for viaducts/bridges inspections.

Tunnel

The European Drone Regulation does not apply to indoor operations. Then, it does not apply to the tunnel scenario with the TT-DRONE. In this specific case, the only requirements to be fulfilled are the ones related to HSE (Health & Safety Environment) to be defined by the company that owns or manages the tunnel.

Then, all the PILOTING flight experiments, except the ones in the tunnel scenario, must comply with:

- The category sets the operational limits, depending on whether it is "open" or "specific".
- All the required flight authorisations and applicable mitigation measures.

Analysing now each subcategory of operation, we can conclude that:

Open Category

Due to the nature of PILOTING inspections and their location, in most of the cases the A3 subcategory applies. In this subcategory, three different types of UAS can be operated:

- C3 or C4 labelled drones
- Private built

The labelled drones require to pass through a conformity process with a homologated notified body. Since this process has a high cost, PILOTING UAS will be first operated as privately built, and in the future (exploitation/industrialisation stage), it could be certified to be C3 or C4 labelled.

Specific Category

Since PILOTING does not count with labelled drones since all the UAS are completely new, incorporating cutting edge technologies, most of the flights under the Specific category will be performed under the Operational authorisation option. However, there is an exception for the viaduct case where the Spanish STS02 national standard scenario could be applied. However, this option can only be applied during PILOTING project since after 1st of January 2024, only labelled C6 drones could be used in the European STS 2 standard scenario. This is an important issue to consider in the future exploitation and industrialization of the project results.

Finally, Table 5 sets in which category will operate each of the aerial robots and developed in PILOTING by scenario and what are the operational requirements based on this.

PILOTING Scenario	Robot	Category	Operational Requirements
Refineries	AEROX	Specific	Operational authorisation
	HYBRID	Specific	Operational authorisation

Bridges/Viaducts	AERO-CAM	Open	A3 subcategory: Private built
		Specific	Operational authorisation
	VIAD- DRONE	Open	A3 subcategory: Private built
		Specific	Operational authorisation
Tunnel	TT-DRONE	N/A	N/A

Table 5. Guidelines for then impact assessment in legal (UAV regulation) aspects within PILOTING.

UGV

As was commented in D9.1, for the UGV's test in the framework of PILOTING project there is not a specific regulation. PILOTING covers unmanned ground robots which will be conducted in private properties, so no specific operational requirements are needed.

However, PILOTING UGV developers will consider all the standards and recommendations covered to automated guided vehicles, defined in the **ISO 3691-4:2020** also known as the **Safety requirements and verification Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems vehicles**. This norm specifies safety requirements and the means for their verification for driverless industrial trucks (hereafter referred to as trucks) and their systems. This regulation also describes different procedures and features to comply with, mainly related with stability, speed control, person detection or braking systems.

In addition, as was mentioned below, if one of the current conditions change and the need for further validation tests in public spaces appear, the option of framing such tests define a 'regulatory sandbox', in one of the countries of the consortium member entities would be considered.

ATEX

The ATEX directive considers explosive atmospheres in refineries as an important source of hazard for which the applied equipment must be safe. This regulatory framework (see section 3.6) is necessary to know since one of the main use cases of the PILOTING project is refineries. However, this directive was designed with static and fixed equipment in mind. For mobile systems, and due to the difficulties of applying ATEX directive, Oil&Gas industry has started to design emergency operational procedures to use non-ATEX equipment in hazardous areas.

As was presented in the section 3.6, when a company performs a work on a refinery, there are two main approaches: use ATEX-certified tools or work under a hot-work permit using portable gas detectors together with emergency procedures. After studying this issue in detail (during the definition of the proposal, including workshops with experts in ATEX certification from well-known certification companies), it has been concluded that the best way to handle this barrier in PILOTING,

due to the limitations in budget and time of the R&D project, is the use hot-work permits implementing emergency operational procedures.

For example, CHEVRON has since 2016 “Guidance Notes for Inspection using Unmanned Aircraft Systems” that defines the minimum requirements to be fulfilled by the aerial robot equipment, and its crews, in order to perform operations inside a refinery. Therefore, PILOTING project will pursue a two-way approach:

- It will take into consideration best practices design guidance for the Oil&Gas sector (including a number of ATEX requirements) in order to minimize the risk of explosion when using robotic systems in refineries.
- It will perform complete safety assessments and design emergency operational procedures in order to satisfy refinery owners’ requirements. This specific safety procedure shall be developed in order to address the risks associated with robotic system operations. Impacts on the design and capabilities of the robotic systems should be anticipated in the frame of this project. In particular, the following concerns should be considered:
 - Gas detector on-board the robot with real time communication.
 - “What if” in case of gas detection, design an emergency procedure:
 - i. In case of an aerial robot: robot flies automatically away from the area.
 - ii. In case of a hybrid-robot in crawling mode: robot secures itself on the piping and power is immediately shutdown.
 - iii. In case of a ground robot or crawler: robot stops immediately and power is immediately shutdown.

Finally, commented that PILOTING consortium will keep updated about the unmanned vehicles that will be certified with ATEX, like UGVs (see section 3.6), in order to take into account any possible inputs in the development of the PILOTING solution

4.4 Guidelines for the impact assessment which applies to each PILOTING Impact Scenario

To finalise the definition of the guidelines to perform the 2nd Impact Assesmente (Deliverable D9.4) , Table 6 summarises which of the defined SoEL requirements and principles apply to each impact scenario. This will allow to perform the Impact Assessment considering all the relevant principles of data protection (societal), legal and ethics that apply to the project outcomes and activities concerning their impact.

Impact Scenarios	Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	UAV regulation ATEX requirements

Impact Scenario 2: Refinery -Crawler	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	ATEX requirements
Impact Scenario 3: Refinery- UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	ATEX requirements UGV standards and recommendations covered in the ISO 3691-4:2020
Impact Scenario 4: Bridge/Viaduct- UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	UAV regulation
Impact Scenario 5: Tunnel – UAV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	-
Impact Scenario 6: Tunnel - UGV	GDPR (if necessary)	Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and AI ACT principles	UGV standards and recommendations covered in the ISO 3691-4:2020

Table 6. Applicable SoEL requirements to each PILOTING Scenario.

5. Impact assessment methodology

The primary aim of the PILOTING impact assessment will be to assess potential impacts of the application of the PILOTING project in terms of adherence to the societal, legal and ethical principles outlined in the previous sections.

To the 2nd Impact Assessment report, two different approaches will be taken into consideration:

On one hand, the impact assessment methodology already defined in deliverable D9.1, has been maintained: SoEL impact assessment identification, SoEL impact assessment analysis, and SoEL impact assessment evaluation and treatment.

On the other hand, PILOTING consortium has worked to obtain inputs from an external expert SoEL body on the issues related to the development of PILOTING technologies. The selected body has been the H2020 European project [Robotics4EU](#) (H2020-ICT-2020-2, ID:101017283), which has carried out an in-depth study to evaluate the non-technological aspects (ethical, social, legal, data and education and society engagement) of robotics in the focus areas of the project (being one of them inspection and maintenance of infrastructures).

Next, a summary of these steps, highlighting what is new with respect to what was defined in deliverable D9.1.

5.1 SoEL Impact Assessment Identification

An important part of the impact assessment is the conduction of a clear and consistent risk identification and statement.

The impact assessment will cover the following main areas: privacy and data protection, unmanned vehicles and novel technologies. For each of these areas (privacy and data protection, unmanned vehicles and novel technologies) main SoEL potential risks, that will need to be addressed within the context of SoEL aspects of the PILOTING project, will be tackled in terms of the defined requirements. Each of these requirements will represent an obstacle that the PILOTING project will have to overcome or ensure that the benchmark requirements are met within the context of PILOTING as a project, and also by the deployment of any element created within that project.

To help the identification of possible risks related with non-compliance with SoEL requirements, PILOTING consortium will employ questionnaires. During the 1st Impact Assessment report (D9.2) analysis, the questionnaires were focused on the project developments and distributed only among the PILOTING partners. Since the project involves all the actors that conform the full value chain of the I&M sector, including: high-profile research and innovation partners, world-leading technological companies, highly specialised SMEs, inspection and maintenance service providers, and companies that operate or own infrastructure in both the oil and gas and civil infrastructure/transport sectors, we believe that the answers collected of the project partners could generate a complete view for the SoEL impact assessment identification. However, in the next version of the deliverable (D9.4), new questionnaires will be defined and distributed among a wider audience, also involving external stakeholders and members of the I&M industry. These questionnaires will be more focused on the foreseen applications of PILOTING solution are in line with the SoEL.

The result of this new version will be an updated list of risks, once the PILOTING solution is further developed. To help the identification of risks, the following type of questions will be posed and requested to be answered in D9.4:

1. Do you have experience in applying the GDPR regulation to inspection tasks?
2. During the inspection and maintenance procedures, do you think it could be possible that there are non-involved people in the vicinity to the personnel who carry out the inspection works?
3. Do you know if your company currently applies AI solutions to the inspection processes?
4. Are you aware of any specific regulation or European Comission guidelines that the implemented AI-based algorithms should fulfil?
5. Within your company, is there any previous experience in using UAVs for any inspection application?
6. Do you know if your company has a department or person in charge of verifying compliance with UAV regulation?
7. Are you aware of any specific requirement, regulation or standard that UGVs have to fulfill before using it in your company?

5.2 SoEL Impact Assessment Analysis

PILOTING is a multidisciplinary project with different work streams, operating within different specialisms and forms of expertise. Then, it is important that all the partners involved in the project will analyse the answer to the questionnaires in order to analyse the identified potential risks. A specific workshop with all the partners will be organized in order to get a consensus, taking into account the different expertise of all the partners. Moreover, the following type of questions will be posed and requested to be answered in the Impact assessment report regarding each identified risk:

- What is the likelihood of occurrence of this risk?
- What is the magnitude of the impact should this risk occur?

5.3 SoEL Impact Assessment Evaluation and treatment

The answers provided by each partner during the Impact Assessment analysis workshop, with their expertise in their specific context within the PILOTING project, will allow an accurate evaluation of whether adequate steps have been taken in terms of meeting the requirements that relate to the risks identified.

Such answers will be used to create an impact assessment report (Deliverable 9.4) that will outline what steps have been taken and whether these are sufficient in order to meet the requirements that has been outlined in the previous section. When the steps taken have not been sufficient, the evaluation report will, through consultation with the relevant partners, outline what further steps may be necessary to ensure that the requirements that are identified are met. Also, the following types of questions will help to carry out the update of the Impact assessment evaluation and treatment:

- What mitigating measures have been already implemented or will be implemented to minimise or avoid risks?
- Are there any residual risks left? If yes, are they justified?

All the work performed during these three steps will be documented in the next version of the Impact assessment report (D9.4) that is due M36.

Finally, it is important to remark that, in addition to completing a new impact assessment report, the 2nd Impact Assessment Report (D9.4), will include a description about how the SoEL risk identified in the 1st Impact Assessment Report (D9.2) are being monitored, as well an updated of these risks, more focused on the project developments.

5.4 Consultation of a SoEL expert ethical body

The PILOTING consortium has maintained a cross-border communication with the Robotics4EU Project developers as part of the SoEL risks analysis since they can contribute from an experienced position about the application of robotic technology in society.

The aim of Robotics4EU Project is to expand the use of AI-based robotic platforms in sectors such as healthcare, inspection and maintenance of infrastructure, agri-food, and agile production. To achieve this goal, it will be necessary to implement responsible robotic principles among the robotic community that could result in the acceptance of the society about robotic solutions.

Robotics4EU will create and empower the EU robotic community that represents from companies and academia to citizens, users and even policy makers developing awareness about the non-technological issues of robotics. The Project will develop a maturity assessment model for this, in order to bring the Project results to standardization bodies.

In order to fulfill the previous goal, Robotics4EU will follow the itinerary set by the activities below:

1. Assess the needs and develop a responsible robotics maturity assessment model.
2. Empower the robotics community by organising capacity building events in several fields.
3. Ensure social acceptance of robotics and assess robotics ideas and applications provided by the industry with end-users.
4. Reach out to the policy makers by compiling a responsible robotics advocacy report, organising a high-level policy debate and transfer the results to the standardization bodies.

With their expertise, five main topics were identified in this initiative. These topics are shown with the main preoccupations in society below:

- **Ethical issues**
 - Safety and security at workplace.
 - Lack of responsibility and accountability.
 - Lack of transparency.
 - Lack of liability.
- **Socio-Economics issues**
 - Fear of technological unemployment.
 - Rising skill gaps and skill depreciation.
 - Loss of worker autonomy.
- **Legal issues**
 - Unclear and unharmonized regulations.
 - Lack of and lag in regulatory development.
 - Intellectual property infringement.
- **Data issues**
 - Surveillance issue.
 - Vulnerability of cyber physical systems.
 - Lack of contestability.
- **Education and Society engagement issues**
 - Education issues.
 - Inequality in development.
 - Lack of methods for engagement and empowerment.

Then, the collaboration with this project has been very useful since it has made possible to analyse whether there are any other requirements relating to SoEL that have not been addressed before. This input has been used in the update of the SoEL impact assessment (D9.4). Also, we plan to use the methodology and knowledge acquired by the Robotics4EU framework to further analyse the SoEL risks by an external expert for the set of technologies that we will select to develop an industrialization plan as part of WP10 activities during the last year of the project.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable has provided an upgrade of the ethical principles for the impact assessment related to Social, Ethical and Legal requirements included in the D9.1, setting the basis to complete the 2nd “PILOTING Impact Assessment ” report (D9.4). This work has been performed as part of the continuous monitoring of the impacts upon SoEL requirements, updating to the PILOTING partners with the relevant principles that must follow in the project development and considering in the PILOTING solution design.

After that, the reviewed SoEL aspects to address within PILOTING project are as follows:

- Social aspects: the main applicable legislation concerning privacy and data protection in all PILOTING countries is the GDPR. No changes have been carried out in this regulation since last Periodic Report. This deliverable has reminded the main principles to be applied within the PILOTING project, if necessary. Informed consent procedures must be defined and implemented. The access to the data collected must be restricted only to authorised personnel. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties. A Data Project Officer (DPO) must be appointed.
- Ethical aspect: Regarding the ethical aspects, as was described in the D9.1, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the AI technologies, which is summarised in the "**Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**" [9]. In addition, since the last version of the deliverable, the EC has presented proposal for AI regulation the “**AI ACT 2021**”. Both documents have been analysed to set the ethical principles that must be respected in the development of artificial intelligence algorithms. The "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" establish that the AI development must respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability. The “AI ACT 2021” considers three main categories in which risks can be classified: Unacceptable, High and Limited and minimal. The AI PILOTING developments will be designed to comply with the limited and minimal risk.
- Legal aspect: the main legal applicable regulation is related with the operation of Unmanned Vehicles. Concerning the UAV: the “**European Drone regulation**”. As was defined in the D9.1, the PILOTING project, the aerial platforms developed will be within the categories "open" or "specific". In this new version of the deliverable, the operational requirements within each category have been described: in PILOTING, we work in A3 subcategory: Private Built in “open category” and in Operational authorization in “specific category”. PILOTING aerial robots must always comply with the specifications and operational requirements defined in this regulation. The only exception is the aerial vehicles used in the tunnel scenario where the European Drone regulation does not apply since it is an indoor operation. Related to UGV,

the UGV's test in the framework of PILOTING Project there is not a specific regulation. PILOTING covers unmanned ground robots which will be conducted in private properties, so no specific operational requirements are needed. However, PILOTING UGV developers will take into account all the standards and recommendations covered to automated guided vehicles, defined in the **ISO 3691-4:2020** also known as the Safety requirements and verification Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems vehicles. In addition, a new policy instrument to validate new technologies and solutions without having to wait to have a complete regulation approved to start offering services and products using novel technologies has been analyzed: the "**Regulatory Sandbox**". This has been analyzed as an option to regulate the PILOTING developments related to novel technologies as IA or UGV, in one of the countries where the PILOTING solution will be implemented. Finally, mention that this deliverable has analysed the **ATEX** requirements. Due to the difficulties of applying ATEX directive to dynamic equipment, during the PILOTING experiments will be used hot-work permits, defined by the refinery.

Finally, this deliverable remains an impact assessment methodology to be followed within the Impact Assessment Report (deliverable D9.4). This will be the same as in the previous one (D9.2), adding a new step: collaboration with an external expert ethical body, Robotics4EU, to take into account its experienced position in the application of robotic technology in society.

- Impact assessment Identification: to help the identification of possible risks related to non-compliance with SoEL requirements. To perform this assessment, the PILOTING consortium will employ questionnaires, which have been restructured to be addressed to a wider audience (in the first version of the deliverable these were answered by PILOTING partners).
- Impact assessment analysis: the quantification and qualification of the risk identified in this new iteration.
- Impact assessment evaluation and treatment: A contingency plan will be defined to avoid/minimise each identified risk.
- Consultation of a SoEL expert ethical body: a cross-border communication with the Robotics4EU project, expert in ethical issues, has been established in order to have an expert point of view to analyze the SoEL risks inherent to the PILOTING Project together with the questionnaires used for deliverable D9.4.

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Annex I: “European Drone Regulation”: Categories of operation

The new framework will introduce three categories of operation (open, specific and certified) according to the level of risks involved. A different regulatory approach will be adopted for each category. Low-risk operations ("open" category) will not require any authorisation, but will be subject to strict operational limitations. For medium risk operations, operators will have to require an authorisation from the national aviation authority on the basis of a standardised risk assessment or a specific scenario (specific category). Finally, in case of high risk operations, classical aviation rules will apply (certified category).

Open category

Operations in the open category do not require prior authorisations or pilot license. However, they are limited to operations: in visual line of sight (VLOS), below 120 m altitude and performed with a privately built drone or a drone compliant with the technical requirements defined in the regulation. To demonstrate this compliance drones that can be operated in the open category will bear a class identification label (based on CE marking). Additional operational restrictions apply to each class of drone, in particular with regard to the distance that must be maintained between the drone and non-involved persons.

Specific category

When the intended operation exceeds the restrictions of the "open" category, the operator should consider operating under the "specific" category (medium risk). Only high-risk operations require compliance to classical aviation rules under the "certified" category (like operating in controlled airspace). Operations involving drones of more than 25 kg and/or operated beyond visual line of sight will typically fall under the "specific" category.

Before starting an operation in the specific category, operators must either perform a risk assessment (using a standardised method – the SORA – that is provided by EASA) and define mitigation measures or verify that they comply with a specific scenario defined by EASA (or the national aviation authority). On that basis they will be able to obtain an authorisation from the national aviation authority (in some cases a simple declaration may be enough). The authorisation or the specific scenario will define the authorised operation and the applicable mitigation measures (drone technical requirements, pilot competence, etc.).

Certified Category

The "certified" category (high risk) includes operations involving large drones in controlled airspaces. Rules applicable to the "certified" category will be the same as for manned aviation: drones must be certified for their airworthiness, pilots shall be licensed, and safety oversight will be performed by the relevant National Aviation Authorities and EASA.